

PROMOTION OF PERSONNEL LABOR AND ITS ECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE, SIGNIFICANCE

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Annotation. The article put forward scientific and theoretical foundations for employee motivation, the concept of incentives that should be applied to employees, and its coverage on the basis of feedback from economic scientists. Through incentives, the economic importance of positively influencing the work activity of the employee and providing incentives in labor activities is also covered.

Keywords: employee motivation, scientific and theoretical foundations. The concept of incentives, economic scientists, economic importance, positive impact.

Dispositional theories of labor theory of the need for achievements (D. McClelland). The activities of employees depend on their level of need for achievements or incentive for achievement (the desire to achieve something meaningful, do the job well, be the best). The higher the achievement incentive, the higher the labor efficiency, and vice versa. Studies have shown that the economic growth of organizations and societies may be associated with the level of incentives for the achievements of employees and citizens.

Economic function: Manifested in the promotion of Labor, promotion of production efficiency. It finds expression in the increase in labor productivity and in the improvement of product quality.

Social function: it is ensured by the formation of the social system of society taking into account the different levels of income. And these incomes largely depend on the influence of incentive factors on different people. And in general, it is well known that the formation of needs depends on the development of personality at the ultimate level, the organization and stimulation of labor in society.

Picture 1

Picture 1. Types of incentives¹

The theory of the hierarchy of needs (A. Maslow) he identified 5 basic needs (vital needs, the need for security, the need for communication and love for others, the need for respect, the need for self-realization) and placed them in a pyramid in order to increase their significance for a person. It is established that if the need of a lower level is not satisfied, then the need of a higher level cannot be fully satisfied. Therefore, in order to increase the motivation of work, the employer must create conditions for consistent satisfaction of the needs of the employee. Thus, the conditions that allow interaction with colleagues satisfy the need for communication; the praise of the boss, providing them with a comfortable workplace - the need for respect; the possibility of professional growth and career growth - the need for self-realization.²

Motivational-hygienic (two-factor) theory (F. Herzberg) identified 2 types of needs: incentive needs and hygienic needs.

Needs - incentives are determined by those attributes of work that stimulate high labor productivity (individual production tasks, level of personal responsibility, achievements, recognition, encouragement, career growth and professional growth). Satisfaction of job satisfaction needs. Hygienic needs are determined by the external parameters of the employee (organizational policy, leadership, interpersonal relationships, physical conditions in the workplace, wages, forms of incentives). Dissatisfaction with hygienic needs; dissatisfaction with work.³

¹ Abdurakhmanov K.X. and others. Personal management. Labor publishing. Tashkent 2007y.

² Abdurakhmanov K.X. and others. Personal management. Labor publishing. Tashkent 2007y.

³ E.P. Ilyin. Motivation and motives. - St. Petersburg: Peter, 2011. 263 pages

Cognitive theories of labor motivation general theory of expectations (V. Varlaama). Labor efficiency is determined by the expectation of wages for the correct performance of work. The more a person wants to receive a reward, the harder he is willing to work for it, if his value for him is undeniable. The material incentive of an employee means all the expenses of the employer on the basis of an employment contract.

The main purpose of financial incentives is to direct the activities of personnel to achieve the strategic goals of the company or firm, in other words, it is aimed at combining the material interest of personnel with the strategic goals of the enterprise. This defining rule defines the following objectives of financial incentives:

Attracting an employee to the enterprise. Enterprises compete with each other in the labor market in order to attract the right specialists to work. Therefore, financial incentives should be adequate so that the company can attract the necessary personnel to work.

Employee retention in the company. When the material incentives at the enterprise are below the level offered by the labor market, employees begin to lose their jobs. The head of the enterprise needs to provide financial incentives to employees to the extent that they can compete with other firms and firms, so that the funds spent on professional training and development are not wasted.

Used literature.

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